

Studies on the effect of organized media and nanoparticles on the physical and chemical properties of some organic and inorganic molecules in solution^ψ

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In dilute aqueous solution, amphiphilic substances (surfactants), such as long-chain fatty acid salts, quaternary ammonium salts, carboxylates etc. behave as simple organic molecules. At higher concentration, however, they no more show the ideal behavior of their dilute solutions. These deviations are different from those exhibited by simple strong electrolytes. In the higher concentration range, the amphiphiles form dynamic aggregates, i.e. micelles, which change some of the physical properties of the surfactants. The related physical properties are interfacial tension, electrical conductivity, solubility, pH, transport properties like viscosity and spectroscopic properties. The concentration at which the aggregates are formed and manifest distinct physical properties is called the critical micellar concentration (CMC). Depending on the chemical structure of the surfactants, the micelles can be classified as cationic, anionic, non-ionic or zwitterionic.

The surfactant-mediated reactions are now increasing the potential industrial utility in different fields like pharmacy, photography, extraction, polymerization etc. In some cases, these systems also provide models for membrane mimetic processes. Different organic and inorganic compounds change their solubility, dissociation constant values etc. in micellar media. Aqueous solution of micelle creates the environment for the interaction of two or more reactants and facilitates the reactions. Micellar catalysis¹⁻⁵ reactions are now well mentioned in different reviews. Rate acceleration or retardation of organic reactions in micellar solutions arises from different rates of the reaction of substrate in the micellar phase and in the bulk solution. Basically these rate effects can be attributed to electrostatic and/or hydrophobic interaction between the substrate and the surfactant aggregate. Giving preference to the electrostatic interaction⁶, it can be predicted that cationic micelle enhances the rate of the reactions of nucleophilic anions with uncharged substrate whereas anionic micelle retards them but catalyzes the

reactions involving cations. Uncharged and zwitterionic micelles will have little or no effect on reaction rates. Micellar catalysis tends to be more pronounced for surfactants having longer alkyl chains⁷. Catalysis of some nucleophilic aromatic substitution reactions and particularly of the reactions of fluoride ion with *p*-nitrophenyl-diphenyl phosphate is more pronounced by dicationic micellar surfactants than by cationic micelle, hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide⁸. The increase of hydrophobicity also sometimes changes the rate of the reactions⁹. For most reactions, micellar catalysis is inhibited by counter ions and larger the ion, the greater is the effect¹⁰. Nature of electrolytes also plays a major role during catalysis. Till date, little information regarding the thermodynamics of the interaction of organic and inorganic molecules with micelles is available. The work is in progress to enhance the catalytic efficiency of micelles by exploiting different functionalities and nature of charge on the surfactants and thereby utilizing surfactant aggregates in non-aqueous solvents.

Thus, catalysis involving micelles (aggregates of surfactant) is a vast as well as complicated area of research. There may be acceleration or inhibition of reaction rate by surfactant, above and below CMC. The rate inhibition by the use of buffers and other swamping electrolytes on the micellar catalysis is always an observable fact and hence they are not generally used to study reactions. For obtaining quantitative information involving micelle as catalyst, its interaction with the substrate should be clearly elucidated. One important point to be noted in micellar catalysis is that, for reactions involving inorganic ions, generally hydrophobic interactions are largely neglected. On the other hand, the reverse is true for organic reactions.

Other new field of catalysis involves metal nanoparticles. Because of their surface charge (due to adsorbed

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ions), they reside in the palisade layer of the micellar aggregate. Maintaining their positions, they take part in reactions. To have quantitative and reproducible information of catalysis involving metal nanoparticle, the particles should be stable and well defined in their shape and size. Therefore, micelles become useful entities for synthesis and stabilization of nanoparticles and are often used in solution to study their catalytic effect. Reactions involving nanoparticles in micellar solutions thus become a newer field of modern research because of the following reasons : (i) micelles provide the effective reaction site for the substrate and the incoming reagent, (ii) suitable 'salting-out' and 'salting-in' agents provide clue to the reaction pathways, (iii) by suitable extractions of the substrate, micelles provide fractal surface, (iv) because of the solubilization property of micelle and the dynamic aggregate formation, catalyst surface becomes readily accessible for the promotion of reaction. (v) micelles easily stabilize the nanoparticles, (vi) sometimes, micelles take direct part in nanoparticle synthesis, (vii) micelle controls the size of the nanoparticles, and (viii) sometimes they control the shape of the nanoparticles providing suitable template arising out of the micellar aggregates.

Synthesis of well defined metal nanoparticles, their characterization, distribution and applications to different fields have come to the forefront in modern investigation. Because of the existence of different optical and electronic properties from the bulk, nanoparticles are used in many fields including catalysis, microelectrodes, quantum size effect in photochemistry, semiconductors, etc. One of the most interesting aspects of the studies of metal and semiconductor nanoparticles is their size dependent properties¹¹⁻¹⁷ which are found to be equally important from fundamental as well as application point of view. In case of redox reactions, the electron transfer step may have to overcome a large energy barrier electron transfer from donor to acceptor and it may restrict the passage of electron. For this, a catalyst of intermediate redox potential value of the donor and acceptor, served the best purpose for the electron relay process.

Metal particles are well known examples of these types of catalysts. Recent experiments suggest that when metal particles become smaller in size their redox property differs from the bulk metal and their redox potential changes in the presence of adsorbed foreign ions. Thus different size metal particles having different redox potentials play the role of electron transfer in the presence of foreign ions. However, intermediate stage of the growing metal particles is neglected, though their properties are quite different in the final stage¹⁸⁻²¹. These subcolloidal particles are formed as short-lived intermediates during the reduction of metal ions and act as seeds for the growth of metal colloids²⁰⁻²⁴. The redox potential of these particles in the growing stage con-

tinuously changes, so also redox properties. Hence the reaction kinetics of the catalytic reaction change with growing (GME) and full grown (FGME) particles. Unlike these growing particles, metal sols are used for catalysis because of their better stability and well understood physicochemical properties^{21,25-30}. Such systems are macroscopically homogeneous but microscopically heterogeneous. This plays the important role for the microheterogeneous systems to act as a catalyst utilizing both their homogeneous and heterogeneous catalytic properties. In comparison, the use of growing small particles as catalyst is limited due to their short lifetime^{20,23,31}. Sometimes, they are stabilized in suitable solid matrix³²⁻³⁶ or by surface modification using appropriate ligands^{21,30} or polymers^{37,38} and have been used in heterogeneous catalysis. This type of stabilization always leads to the loss of catalytic activity to a great extent. Solid matrices/ligands strongly interact with surface atoms occupying a good number of the active sites of the catalysts. For polymers, though their interactions might not be so strong with the catalyst surface, steric effects from these bulky species come into play in the vicinity of the catalyst surface^{39,40}. In this regard, surfactants are recommended as viable alternatives⁴¹. They are loosely packed and their dynamic structures around the catalyst surface stabilize the particles but hardly affect the accessibility of the particles to the reacting molecules. Moreover, surfactant leaves a control over the rate of synthesis and particles size without unduly diminishing the active surface area of the catalyst.

Here, our attempt is to show how a micellar medium removes the kinetic barrier of simple electron transfer reactions by increasing the encounter probability between the reactants. Moreover, we report the size dependent catalytic activity of coinage metal nanoparticles for reduction of dye molecules and nitrocompounds⁴². Simple photo-activation reaction in micelle has also been examined to produce particles to achieve the important goal of producing different sized (successive increase in size) monodispersed particles in the nano domain⁴³. Simple and commonly used surfactants are cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) (cationic), sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) (anionic) and poly(oxyethy-lene)iso-octylphenyl ether (TX-100 or Triton X-100) (non-ionic) and we have used them for different purposes in aqueous solutions as normal micelles. They were used in a concentration range where all of them are known to form spherical micelles. All the absorption spectra were monitored in a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cuvette. TEM measurement was carried at 400 kV using JEOL 4000 EX instrument. Sample was prepared by placing a drop of solution containing nanoparticles on a carbon coated Cu grid.

Micellar catalysis

The reaction between ascorbic acid (2.5×10^{-4} M, AA)

and methylene blue ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$, MB) were performed in aqueous alkaline (pH ~ 10) solution as well as different micellar medium to study the kinetic results. The reaction involves micellar catalysis. The progress of the reaction, i.e. the reduction of MB was monitored from the colour bleaching of the cationic dye, MB (λ_{\max} 665 nm) and was quantified using a visible spectrophotometer. As no electronic spectral shift (λ_{\max} 665 nm) of MB was observed even after the interaction of MB with the micelles, all measurements were done at 665 nm. In water, no appreciable bleaching of the colour (i.e. the reduction) of the dye was noticed but in TX-100 and SDS bleaching was observed to be very slow. However, in CTAB it proceeds instantaneously and the reduced MB (colourless) was obtained in the aqueous micellar solution⁴⁴.

The reducing agent AA could not reduce MB in simple aqueous solution though this is a thermodynamically favorable reaction condition. In strongly alkaline solution, AA becomes stronger reducing agent (AA^-) even then no appreciable reduction of MB could be observed in the experimental time-scale. The interesting point is that MB (cationic dye) and ascorbate ion (AA^-) are oppositely charged species but transfer of electron did not take place from AA^- to MB. Presumably a kinetic barrier inhibits the interaction of the two species to show any progress of the reaction. But in cationic micellar solution (CTAB), the kinetic barrier is removed and MB starts reacting. In CTAB complete reduction of MB occurred in the presence of AA when the ratio, micelle : MB > 3. This optimum micelle-to-MB ratio is a necessary condition for quantitative incorporation of the dye into the micelle. At a lower concentration of micelle some of the MB remained in the bulk (i.e. remained unbound and outside the micelle) and hence micellar catalysis was not observed for that unbound amount of MB. In that case it was difficult to study the reaction with some amount of micelle bound as well as unbound (free) MB. The reaction between MB and AA^- becomes thermodynamically favorable in CTAB solution (the activation energy were experimentally determined to be 114 kJ mol^{-1}) but it does not happen in aqueous medium. This may be due to the lack of proper encounter probability as the reactants are solvated or having high activation energy. However, the reaction rate did not increase in SDS and TX-100 micellar medium.

The catalysis involving micelle changes the environment of the reaction with decreasing free energy difference between the initial and the transition state. This also increases the frequency of collisions as a consequence of the close association of the reactants at the micellar interface. This can also be rationalized in terms of bringing together the reactants MB and AA^- into the micellar Stern layer. More favorable binding of the substrate in micelles leads to a higher encounter probability. Micelle surfaces bind many

Fig. 1. Schematic representation for the incorporation of dye (MB) and the reductant in CTAB, SDS and TX-100 micellar solution.

organic and inorganic compounds by electrostatic and/or hydrophobic interaction⁴⁵. In this case, MB being a cationic dye binds to CTAB by hydrophobic force and AA^- ion binds to CTAB through hydrophobic as well as electrostatic forces. Thus the two reagents come to a closer proximity and they react. This explains quantitatively the faster rate of reduction of MB in the CTAB micellar surface. Here, electrostatic attraction favors the presence of AA^- in the Stern layer of CTAB (Fig. 1). In TX-100 micelle, MB easily finds an avenue to be incorporated in the micelle by hydrophobic force and some AA^- may diffuse into the Stern layer (Fig. 1). So the reduction of MB was observed in this nonionic micelle. MB being a cationic dye binds to the anionic micelle SDS by both electrostatic as well as hydrophobic interactions. However, charge repulsion removes the AA^- ions from the Stern layer (Fig. 1) and hence practically no reaction was observed. When only one of the substrates is adsorbed, then the encounter probability is reduced and hence micellar catalysis is hindered. Thus

the observed rate of reductions is CTAB > TX-100 > SDS. The binding for MB is facilitated in all the three micelles by hydrophobic interaction. However, the difference in the behavior between any one of the three micelles may be due to the differing availability of AA⁻ in the Stern layer of the micelles, which in turn is incorporated mainly by electrostatic interactions. The interaction of MB (hydrophobic interaction) with the micelle is once again supported by the decrease in the rate of reduction of dimethylmethylen blue (DMMB) in comparison to MB reduction. The DMMB having more hydrophobic character than MB penetrates deep into the non-polar interior of CTAB micelles. Thus, DMMB is less accessible to AA⁻.

It has been found that for the reduction of 1×10^{-5} M MB by the 2.5×10^{-4} M AA⁻ at pH ~10, the rate is not appreciably accelerated by metal particles while an equal concentration of NaBH₄ efficiently catalyzes the reaction. Under the same reaction condition, the rate of micellar catalysis in the presence of AA⁻ is much higher than the reaction rate in the presence of metal particles. The rate of reduction by the AA⁻ at pH ~10 follows the order : CTAB > H₂O ~Au⁰ ~Ag⁰ ~Cu⁰. Thus metal particles do not function as efficient catalyst for the reaction in the presence of AA⁻. Using BH₄⁻ as the reductant, the rate of reduction (at pH ~10) in the presence of metallic Au is ~14 times than that in water. The reaction rate in this case follows the order : Au⁰ > Ag⁰ > Cu⁰ > H₂O.

Next, the rate of aerial oxidation of reduced MB in the presence of surfactants and of metal particles was probed. As in the case of reduction, the rate of back-oxidation in the presence of metal particles is observed to be much faster in the presence of BH₄⁻, than in AA⁻. Experimentally, it was observed that on addition of BH₄⁻, the absorbance almost instantaneously decreases to a very low value in the presence of Ag and Au particles and then it gradually increases and finally remains constant at a value very close to the original. For copper, however, the rate of reduction by BH₄⁻ is slower.

The redox reaction between MB and the reductant can be viewed as an electron transfer reaction. The reason for the rate enhancement in the presence of metal particles can be simply explained as follows. The metal particles possess a large surface area, which helps as an entity for the electron transfer reaction. Initially, both of the reactants were adsorbed on the surface of the metal particles. Subsequently, the reductant releases the electron to the metal particles from where MB gains an electron and is thus reduced. In the absence of particles, the reacting species exhibits rapid diffusing motions thereby reducing the chances of fruitful encounters. The metal particle surface acts as an efficient catalyst by being involved in the electron transfer process. Earlier studies have reported that electron transfer

reaction occurs via colloidal particles^{29,46}. Under such conditions, the particles are found to pick up a mixed potential which is anodic to the reductant and cathodic to the oxidant^{26,27}. Such potentials depend on the size of the particles and the nucleophile present⁴⁷. Thus, higher the electron injection capacity of a nucleophile, the more cathodic will be the shift in redox potential⁴⁷. Once the reaction gets started, the rate will, most probably, be driven by the potential difference between the particle and the electron acceptor. The higher efficiency of the BH₄⁻ ion in the reduction reaction can thus be explained. The standard electrode potential of BH₄⁻ is highly negative ($E^{\circ} = -1.48$ V, SCL). For AA⁻, the electron injection capacity being much less, the rate of reduction is lower than that of BH₄⁻. The more efficient catalysis of the MB reduction by gold particles can be explained by the stronger binding of Au with the sulfur atom of MB. There are reports of the binding of gold with thiols^{48,49}.

A similar experiment was repeated for the reduction of MB with SnCl₂ (reducing agent) in lieu of AA. In aqueous medium the observed rate of reduction of MB with SnCl₂ was too slow compared to the reaction in CTAB micellar medium. However in TX-100 the rate is intermediate, and for SDS, the reaction could not be monitored due to precipitation.

SnCl₂ is a celebrated reducing agent and widely used in solution involving active Sn^{II} ion ($\text{Sn}^{4+} + 2e = \text{Sn}^{2+}$; $E^{\circ} = +0.172$ V) for reduction purpose. However, with the increase in HCl concentration, SnCl₂ essentially becomes SnCl₃⁻ ($\text{SnCl}_2 + \text{HCl} = \text{HSnCl}_3$) or SnCl₄²⁻ ($\text{SnCl}_2 + 2\text{HCl} = \text{H}_2\text{SnCl}_4$) ion⁵⁰. The appropriate half-reaction may be $\text{SnCl}_6^{2-} + 2e = \text{SnCl}_3^- + 3\text{Cl}^-$ (1 M HCl and 4 M Cl⁻). Anyway, higher concentration of HCl makes SnCl₂ a stronger reducing agent. It has been observed that the Sn^{II} ion in the presence of higher concentration of HCl enhances the reduction rate of MB in CTAB as well as in TX-100. This may be due to the enhancement of reducing property of the Sn^{II} ion after the formation and then incorporation of anionic Sn^{II} species, in micelle. The ion association of the complex species with CTAB, i.e. with the cationic micelle, was further verified by the solvent extraction. So the active reducing agent is SnCl₃⁻ or SnCl₄²⁻. This acts similar to AA⁻ in the reduction process of MB. So this again speaks the hydrophobic interaction that supercedes the electrostatic interaction, and the observed first order rate constant of the reduction with respect to MB is 0.086, 0.303 and 0.167 min⁻¹ for water, CTAB and TX-100 medium, respectively.

The water-hydrocarbon interactions are modified in the presence of additives^{51,52}. It is widely known that urea and big ions (guanidinium, Gdm⁺; ClO₄⁻) disrupt hydrophobic aggregation. Since these compounds lead to increased

solubility of organic molecules in an aqueous medium, they are called 'salting-in-agents'. Small ions (Li^+ , Na^+ , Cl^- etc.) reduce the solubility of organic compounds in water and hence are called 'salting-out-agents'. The latter facilitate hydrophobic binding.

Both the cases of MB reduction (by AA^- or SnCl_2) strengthen the contention that hydrophobic effect is an important factor affecting the rate of reduction of MB ($0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) by SnCl_4^{2-} ($0.13 \times 10^{-2} M$) or AA ($2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$) in CTAB ($10^{-2} M$) and TX-100 ($10^{-2} M$), the effect of various salts have been examined. Experimentally it was found that the rate of complete reduction of MB in CTAB led to delay when $0.1 M$ urea and $1.0 M$ guanidinium hydrochloride were added. In presence of $0.1 M$ LiCl, the reduction of MB has been observed to be accelerated. This proves the importance of salting-out action of LiCl in the reaction. A similar effect happened when TX-100 was used as surfactant in place of CTAB. It was found that at the same dye concentration, the rate of reduction by any of the two reducing agents slowed down when $0.1 M$ urea, $1.0 M$ guanidinium hydrochloride and $0.2 M$ LiClO₄ were added. In presence of $0.1 M$ LiCl, the reduction in TX-100 showed the usual acceleration in rate.

Formation and growth of metal clusters and their characteristics in solution

The application of extremely small metal particles (metal cluster) was investigated in our laboratory at the end of 1980s. Reviews of the work on this have already been published¹⁹⁻²¹. The first goal was to generate their stable particle dispersion as a quantitative measure for the development of various analytical procedures. It soon became evident that these colloidal particles are quite useful for studying the oxygen-dependent dissolution of metal nanoparticles with various complexing agents. After about a decade or so we rediscovered the metal particles and learnt that they lie in the nanometer size domain and they are of immense importance in nanotechnology. Throughout the globe the metal nanoparticles are produced by reducing metal salts following wet chemical technique⁵³⁻⁵⁵, radiation chemical process⁵⁶⁻⁶¹ or thermal decomposition process⁶². There is a transition from bulk metallic to molecular properties for the metal nanoparticles. So scientists and technologists are very much interested with the 'neglected dimension' of metals for material research in particular.

Small metal particles are more difficult to handle, as they are sensitive towards oxygen⁶³. It is of special interest to study the changes in the optical properties of the particles when they are exposed to chemicals. Silver and gold are most useful for this kind of study because of the presence of very rich surface plasmon bands in the visible region. It is caused by a surface oscillation of the electron gas⁶⁴, where discrete electronic excitations due to interband

transitions occur at shorter wavelengths. In case of copper and gold, the collective and discrete excitations are superimposed. Unfortunately, for copper, palladium and platinum we do not see any rich plasmon peak position in the visible region. So it becomes uninteresting to work with these metal nanoparticles especially in relation to change in the optical properties.

The metal clusters are formed as transient intermediates during the formation of metal colloid by reduction of metal ions in solution. At the initial stage of colloid formation, the metal atoms are produced, which subsequently agglomerate (Scheme 1). The agglomeration steps can be written as $M_{n-1} + M^{x+} + x e = M_n$, where n is the agglomeration number.

Scheme 1

The aggregation process of free clusters in aqueous solution, in the absence of ligands and polymers, does not cease before high values of nuclearity are attended, leading to a colloid and even to a precipitate. It has been known that the clusters can be stabilized by their interaction with an added surfactant or ligand, which as a result of electrostatic repulsion or steric hindrance do the stabilization job. The process follows formation of a few nucleation centers which then catalyzes further reduction on their surfaces or with the formation of large number of nucleation centres with simultaneous agglomerations. However, to restrict the cluster growth it is important to study their size-dependent properties. This process depends on the redox potential of metal/metal ion and the reducing agent, nature of the solvent used, the stabilizing agent and/or the foreign ions present in the solution. Faraday⁶⁵ first produced the aqueous dispersion of gold nanoparticles through the reduction of gold salts by citric acid under boiling condition. That pink gold sol is stable till today, without any other stabilizers added from outside. Actually citrate ions act as the reductant, the excess of it are adsorbed onto the surface of the gold nanoparticles, which inhibit the agglomeration of the gold particles. However, gold nanoparticles can also be made stable in its aqueous solution by the reductant BH_4^- or the complex AuCl_4^- ions. Even today, the citrate-reduction method remains as one of the most reliable methods of producing gold nanoparticles in solution.

The reduction potential of $M^{n+} / M_{\text{nanoparticle}}$ (aqueous) system is lower than that of $M^{n+} / M_{\text{metal}}$ system and depends on particle size and the nature of adsorbed ions at the particle surface. The average particle size does not change appreciably with preparation to influence the particle potential to a significant extent. However, these small metal particles have large surface to volume ratio compared to bulk metal. As a result, adsorption of large number of foreign ions onto the nanoparticle surface is possible^{20,24,47}. These foreign ions can change the particle size distribution as well as the plasmon peak position. The adsorption of nucleophile onto the particle surface increases the Fermi level of the particle due to its donation of electron density to the particle. Similarly, withdrawal of electron density from the particle surface by an electrophile lowers the Fermi level⁶⁶. This is observed as the blue- and red-shift of the plasmon peak. However, sometimes this shift occurs with the immediate addition of surfactant. For this case, the surfactant replaces the surrounded ions. Another observation was the sharpness of the plasmon peak height, which arises due to narrower distribution of particle size with reduced rate of agglomeration. With the gradual increase in addition of NaBH_4 , the band position shows a blue-shift due to the displacement of the surfactant by BH_4^- ion. Again, the band shifts to its original position⁶⁷ while the solution is kept overnight. The auto-decomposition of NaBH_4 results in the reduced electron density on the metal particles and reflects its original condition. In presence of air, the surface of the metal nanoparticles get oxidized by the adsorption of the strong nucleophile like BH_4^- . This was authenticated from the reversible formation and dissolution studies⁶⁸. When AgNO_3 is reduced to silver hydrosol by NaBH_4 ($10^{-3} M$), it leaves a silver plasmon peak at 415 nm. This peak shifts to the blue region (~ 390 nm) in the presence of excess NaBH_4 but never vanishes in water-air mixture on shaking. On the other hand, if the reaction is performed in TX-100 micelle, the peak due to silver plasmon band may appear anywhere in the 380–410 nm region (depending on the amount of excess NaBH_4) and completely vanishes on shaking in air and reappears on standing. In the presence of excess NaBH_4 , the surface of silver nanoparticle becomes vulnerable to oxidation and the oxide layer dissolves in TX-100 if present, otherwise silver particles remain stable with an oxide coating onto its surface. Comparatively, smaller particles of silver could be regenerated with a cleaner surface after removing the oxide layer (or reducing the oxide layer by NaBH_4) in the presence or absence of TX-100 micelle. This is clearly clarified in the latter section of application of nanoparticles in catalysis.

Ligands, polymers or surfactants, especially solvent soluble, which have some affinity for metals, stabilize the metal atoms^{37,67,69}. These substrates can also control the

rate of formation of metal atoms by the reduction of metal ions as well as check the rate of agglomeration. Generally this is done by the formation of metal particles and simultaneous coordination of the stabilizer to metal surface. This process follows the reduction of metal ions and then stabilization of metal particles or coordination of the metal ions with the stabilizer and the reduction in the next step. In the former process, the particle size and shape distribution depend only on the reduction. But the latter process well controls the growth of nanoparticles as the ions are already capped with the stabilizer.

Kamat *et al.*⁷⁰ reported that 80–120 nm colloidal silver shows a plasmon absorption in the visible region when subjected to laser pulse excitation which then breaks up into smaller clusters of 10–40 nm by interparticle charge distribution. El-Sayed *et al.*^{71,72} studied the subpicosecond absorption of passivated gold particles of size 1.9–3.2 nm. They mentioned the bleaching of the plasmon band with varying size of particle. From the most recent studies, it is found that the intense laser heating of gold particles changes its shape and size. Francois *et al.*⁷³ prepared gold sol by γ -irradiation method with gold salt in polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). The atoms are formed with a homogenous distribution throughout the solution. The atoms dimerize when encountered by pairs or associated with excess ions, and these species progressively coalesce into cluster by multi-step process. This coalescence process is being restricted with the stabilizing agent, PVA. Higher the PVA concentration smaller is the final cluster radius. Similarly, when a solution of Au^{III} ions ($3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) in TX-100 solution is irradiated in presence of UV-light for few minutes a pink coloured solution of gold nanoparticles are formed⁶¹. Here TX-100 ($1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$) acts both as a reducing agent as well as a stabilizing agent. The resulting particle size remains ~ 6 nm with an plasmon absorption band at 510 nm.

Yellow sol of silver can also be prepared by simple reduction of AgNO_3 with the reducing agent NaBH_4 even without any stabilizing agent. The procedure needs purging out of the dissolved oxygen under ice-cold condition. In a typical set of experiment of 2 ml AgNO_3 ($10^{-4} M$), N_2 gas is purged for 10 min keeping the system under ice-cold condition and then freshly prepared (ice-cold) NaBH_4 solution (0.02 ml, $10^{-2} M$) is slowly added. This leads to a yellow colored solution with a characteristic absorption band at 395 nm. Keeping the solution for 12 h, this band gives a red-shift of ~ 30 nm but again addition of an excess of NaBH_4 shows the original band. To a solution of 100 ml CuSO_4 ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$), 1 ml of ice-cold NaBH_4 (0.1 M) solution is added, which results in a yellowish brown color and gives the absorbance spectra at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 500$ nm, which is the characteristic of plasmon band of Cu nanoparticles.

In the preparation of Pd particles from PdCl_2 in a buffer solution (pH-6) of TX-100, the particles formed are in the

range of 3–20 nm⁷⁴. The average sizes are 5 nm for NaBH₄, 5 and 7 nm for N₂H₄ at pHs 9.5 and 6.2, and 10 nm for ascorbate ion. The size distribution is broad for ascorbate but very sharp for NaBH₄. With increasing reduction potential of the reducing agent, the average size of the particle increases and the size distribution becomes broad. The average size increases with decreasing pH for hydrazine. This is due to lower reducing power of hydrazine at low pH. The formation of Pd particles were well recognized from the UV-visible spectra (but without any stabilizer) of the solution in the reduction process (Fig. 2). The peak at 250 nm which is due to Pd^{II} ion, decreases with simultaneous formation of new peak at 400 nm, which corresponds to the plasmon peak position of Pd. In the case of the stabilizer, the particle size changes with both the nature and concentration of the stabilizing agent. The well-known yellow sol of silver when prepared in CTAB medium by NaBH₄ reduction, the average particle size remains 65 nm with a sharp plasmon band at 410 nm. But for TX-100 and SDS, the average size remains at 55 and 80 nm with a plasmon peak position at 394 and 392 nm, respectively.

Fig. 2. Successive UV-visible spectra of palladium particles in aqueous solution; [PdCl₂] = 1.43×10^{-5} M, [N₂H₄] = 1.67×10^{-4} M, pH = 9.4.

Stepwise growth of metal clusters by seed mediated method :

We prepared smaller metal particles first and later on, used them as seed particles/nucleation centers for the preparation of the desired particles with larger dimension, so that uncertainty of forming nucleation centers or the importance of impurities is nullified. We applied this procedure for the preparation of Cu, Ag, Au and Pd particles. Initially we produced the metal particles (see particles) with strong reducing agents and then for the successive reduction process weak reducing agents were used. This helps to minimize the formation of new nucleation centers. For the preparation of all the above metal seed particles, N₂ gas was purged in all cases to purge out the dissolved oxygen. The mixture was kept under stirring condition and sometimes an ice-bath was needed. To a solution of 100 ml CuSO₄ (2×10^{-4} M), 1 ml of ice-cold NaBH₄ (0.1 M) solution was added, which resulted in a yellowish brown color giving the absorbance spectra at λ_{\max} 500 nm, the characteristic of plasmon band of Cu nanoparticles (Fig. 3a). For silver seed particles, 10 g trisodium citrate and 7.5 g FeSO₄·7H₂O were

dissolved in 60 ml water and 25 ml solution of AgNO₃ (containing 2.5 g) was added after purging N₂ gas for 10 min. This solution was then diluted to 1 dm⁻³. The resulting solution turned yellow and showed the absorption spectrum at 400 nm (Fig. 3b), which indicated the plasmon peak of silver particles. In case of Au seed preparation, 100 ml aqueous solution of HAuCl₄ (5×10^{-4} M) was boiled and 1 ml of trisodium citrate (0.2 M) solution was added dropwise to it. On boiling and stirring for another 10 min, the solution turned violet indicating the formation of Au nanoparticles. The solution showed the characteristic plasmon band at 525 nm (λ_{\max}) on dilution (Fig. 3c). Pd seed particles were prepared with the addition of ice-cold solution of NaBH₄ (1 ml, 0.1 M) to 100 ml aqueous solution of PdCl₂ (10^{-4} M) with stirring condition. The metal particles were formed immediately, visualized by the appearance of faint black color without any appreciable characteristic plasmon peak in the given region (Fig. 3d). In this way we got all the seed particles as spherical in shape, and the average size of seed particles of Cu, Ag, Au and Pd were 7, 27, 19 and 7 nm, respectively.

Fig. 3. UV-visible spectra of the plasmon absorption peak of (a) Cu, (b) Ag, (c) Au and (d) Pd; [CuSO₄] = 2×10^{-4} M, [NaBH₄] = 0.1 M; [AgNO₃] = 1.4×10^{-2} M [FeSO₄·7H₂O] = 0.27 M; [HAuCl₄] = 5×10^{-4} M, [trisodium citrate] = 0.2 M; [PdCl₂] = 1.0×10^{-4} M; [NaBH₄] = 1.0×10^{-3} M.

In the preparation of successive growth of metal particles, three (A-C) sets of solutions were prepared from the above mentioned seed (S) solution separately. Variable amounts of the respective metal salts were introduced to each seed solution. The solutions were made up to 100 ml by adding distilled water and the dissolved oxygen was removed by purging N₂. Then the solutions were kept under stirring condition and finally, the required amount of freshly prepared ascorbic acid was added slowly to the stirred solution so that the final concentration of the ascorbic acid in each mixture became 10^{-4} M. The [metal salt] : [ascorbic acid] = 1 : 2 was found to serve the purpose well for the reduction of the adsorbed metal ions for the successive growth of the seed particles. Inert N₂ atmosphere was maintained till the addition of ascorbic acid was complete and stirring was continued for another 5 min. To prevent the ag-

gregation of silver particles, trisodium citrate (stabilizer for silver particles) was added (final concentration, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$) prior to the addition of ascorbic acid for the growth of silver particles. The UV-visible spectra of the seed and successive particles (A-C) (Fig. 4a), TEM pictures (S, A-C) and his-

Fig. 4(a). UV-visible spectra : (S) seed, (A-C) successive growth of silver particles.

tograms for Ag particles are shown in Fig. 4b, respectively, for a representative case. Table 1 shows the characteristics and the method of preparation of the metal particles from the seed particles of silver. The mechanism of the formation of the successive growth particles is presented in Scheme 1(c).

Table 1. Conditions and characteristics of the formation of successive growth of silver particles from the seed particles

Silver metal	$[M^0] + [M^+]$ $\times 10^{-4} M$	$[M^0] : [M^+]$ $\times 10^{-4} M$	[Ascorbic acid] $\times 10^{-4} M$	Average size
Ag(A)	2	1 : 2	2	45
Ag(B)	2	1 : 20	2	87
Ag(C)	2	1 : 200	2	105

The seed particles of copper and palladium were produced by NaBH_4 reduction of their salts where FeSO_4 was used for silver with citrate as stabilizer. To reduce HAuCl_4 only citrate was used under boiling condition and unreacted citrate in turn stabilized gold particles. Natan *et al.* have recently described the seeding method for the preparation of gold⁷⁵ (using NH_2OH) and bimetallic nanocolloids of gold coated with silver⁷⁶ without going for the spontaneous reduction of silver ions by 2-propanol and γ -irradiation technique⁷⁷. This is a distinct advantage compared to capping agent/template mediated but restricted growth, where the capping capacity cannot be quantified directly. Thus a general method was developed for the preparation of copper, silver, gold and palladium particles of different size (~10–200 nm). This method has been found to be very useful for the study of size dependent catalytic properties of nano size metal particles in solution. The interesting results were obtained for the formation of copper particles. Under the experimental condition, sodium ascorbate did not reduce cupric ions to copper metal in solution. So little amount of NaBH_4 was used at first during the metallic seed formation of copper. The yellow brown colour of the copper sol solution (λ_{max} 500 nm) is due to plasmon resonance with a significant contribution from in-

Fig. 4(b). TEM pictures and size distribution histograms of seed mediated growth of silver particles : (S) seed, (A-C) successive growth of silver particles.

terband transition. The ascorbate ions reduced the cupric ions on the surface of the copper metal autocatalytically (Scheme 1). In this process almost all the copper seeds exhibited spherical shapes but their further growth in the succeeding steps resulted only cubic particles for always. Electron diffraction showed that the copper nanoparticles were enclosed by six {100} faces and each particle was single crystalline.

Photochemical control of particle size :

Recently, a radiolytic and a chemical size control with improved monodispersity via seed mediated growth of colloidal gold nanoparticles were reported by Henglein and Meisel⁷⁷ and Natan's group^{78,79} respectively. They followed iterative growth method, i.e. particles grown in the

previous step were used as seeds immediately in the next growth step. We developed a method of preparation of gold sol by simple irradiation technique and incorporated this photochemical approach with a non-iterative growth method to develop a simple and fast technique of size control⁴³. Here, particles of various sizes ranging from average diameter 5–20 nm were obtained within a few minutes by UV irradiation at room temperature (28°) in presence of air. Furthermore, larger particles (diameter 25–110 nm) were produced directly from the original seed particles by varying the ratio of original [seed] to $[Au^{III}]$ and using ascorbic acid as reductant. It was noted that ascorbate ion is frequently used as reducing agent for reduction of Au^{III} or Ag^I ions. Goia and Matijevic⁸⁰ recently used iso-ascorbic acid under various pH conditions to synthesize relatively large spherical gold particles (ranging in modal diameter from 80 nm to 5 μ m) directly from Au^{III} ions.

We observed that almost monodispersed gold particles were obtained by UV irradiation of a solution of $HAuCl_4$ in aq. TX-100. The procedure showed excellent reproducibility. UV irradiation technique was used by Zhou *et al.*⁸¹ for shape control of gold particles in the presence of a capping polymer. In the present case, TX-100 serves the purpose of stabilizer as well as reductant which has been reported elsewhere. At 10^{-2} M TX-100, TEM study (Fig. 5) showed that spherical particles were formed in all cases and the size of the particles increased with the increase in the ratio of $[Au^{III}]$ to $[TX-100]$. For example, 4×10^{-5} M $HAuCl_4$ in 1.0×10^{-2} and 1.6×10^{-4} M TX-100 produces

Fig. 5. TEM pictures and size distribution histograms of gold particles in different micellar concentrations of TX-100 : (a) $[HAuCl_4] = 4 \times 10^{-5}$ M, $[TX-100] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ M and (b) $[HAuCl_4] = 4 \times 10^{-5}$ M, $[TX-100] = 1.6 \times 10^{-4}$ M.

particles of average diameter 5.5 and 7 nm, respectively (Fig. 5a,b). Again, 4×10^{-5} M Au^{III} solution in 7.93×10^{-6}

M TX-100 gives particles of average diameter 12 nm⁸². The particle distribution was found to be very sharp in all the cases.

Particles of any described size were prepared in a single step from the original seed by adding and reducing appropriate amounts of Ag^{III} ions to various amounts of seed particles. Ascorbic acid was used as the reductant. Though ascorbate ion (or a combination of ascorbic acid and NaOH) is generally used for the reduction of Au^{III} ions, ascorbic acid itself could not produce gold particles from Au^{III} ions in TX-100 medium. But when a small amount of seed particles was added to the Au^{III} ion system, ascorbic acid immediately started forming gold particles. This showed very weak reducing character of ascorbic acid as well as particle-catalyzed reduction of Au^{III} ions. In principle, in the synthesis of particles of pre-chosen size by seed mediated growth, nucleation and growth steps should be separated from each other and new nucleation and coagulation during the growth stage should be stopped. Therefore, Au^{III} ions should be reduced only onto the existing seed particles in the growth period. It requires a weak reducing agent like ascorbic acid, which would not create any new nucleation center except reducing the ions on the surface of the existing seed particles. The calculated sizes, assuming equal distribution per seed particle, and only surface reduction of Au^{III} ions, agree fairly well with the experimentally (TEM) determined ones. The size of the particle could be calculated²¹ using the equation,

$$d_{\text{final}} = d_{\text{seed}} \{([Au^0] + [Au^{III}] / [Au^0])^{1/3}$$

where d stands for diameter of the particle. In a typical batch, the total amount of gold was kept constant at 5×10^{-4} M in each case, whereas the ratio of $[Au^{III}]$ to $[Au^0]$ in seed was varied between 2 and 100. For this particular condition, the calculated sizes were 33, 50, 72 and 107 nm, respectively. From the TEM study, the respective average sizes were determined to be 31, 51, 82 and 112 nm, which are in very good agreement with the calculated ones. This suggests that ascorbic acid reduces only the surface adsorbed Au^{III} ions creating hardly any new nucleation center.

In another set of experiment the second phase of reduction was again done photochemically. First, the seed particles were prepared and then to it, different amounts of $HAuCl_4$ were added. Further reduction of each set under UV-light in TX-100 medium showed the growth of the Au clusters without formation of new nucleation centers. This is also an example of autocatalytic growth of irradiation technique. A 5.0×10^{-3} M solution of Au^{III} in TX-100 results metal clusters of 18 nm in size. Taking this as seed, when two more sets were prepared with metal and metal ion concentration ratios 1 : 9 and 1 : 99, the particles formed on prolonged irradiation were of sizes 38 and 59 nm.

We also applied this mechanism of catalytic growth by seed particles for preparing bimetallic clusters. Initially Au sol was prepared photochemically in TX-100 and to it AgNO₃ solutions with different concentrations were added. Unlike gold, silver sol could not be prepared by the above photo-irradiation method. But in the presence of Au sol, silver ions got reduced onto the surface of gold particles. This resulted in a bimetallic clusters of a core-shell type structure. These bimetallic clusters have some special properties to be used in catalysis and is discussed elsewhere.

While we were examining the efficiency and usefulness of the photo-activation technique to produce gold nanoparticles, we could develop a very simple method for shape and size control synthesis. Without the use of any template

Bar = 5 μm

Fig. 6. TEM picture of gold particles in 0.5 M TX-100.

we used the iterative growth method for the synthesis of cubic gold nanoparticles in higher concentration of TX-100 micelle. Presumably, the micelle at a very high concentration supplemented templates, which helped the directive growth of the originally produced nucleation centers to achieve cubic shaped gold particles (Fig. 6). In lower micellar concentration spherical gold particles were obtained. We also studied the reaction under stirring condition, but observed stirring did not affect the particle shape and size in 10⁻² M TX-100 micelle. Spherical gold particles of larger diameter were successively produced by the stepwise decrease in the concentration of TX-100 surfactant from its CMC value by keeping the constant amount of Au^{III} solution. Time of irradiation for complete reduction of Au^{III} to Au⁰ depends on the intensity of light used. It has been observed that higher the intensity, the lower would be the time of irradiation for the complete formation of gold nanoparticles.

Nanoparticles and its interactions with different organic and inorganic species

The interaction of organic and inorganic molecules with transition metal surfaces has been attempted in the past. We have reported the reduction of different dyes and some organic nitro compounds using the transition metal nanoparticle catalysts with different reducing agents in aqueous as well as organized media. The dye reductions are thermodynamically favorable but not kinetically. Generally, the

dyes become colorless (or change color) upon reduction and so the progress of the catalytic dye reductions was followed spectrophotometrically. Recent experiments suggest that when the metal particles become smaller in size their redox properties differ from the bulk value and their redox potentials are strongly influenced by the adsorbed foreign ions.

To test the size-dependent catalytic property of metals, the reduction of several dyes and some organic compounds by NaBH₄/N₂H₄/ascorbic acid in presence of the metal salts/metal clusters were considered^{74,83}. The reducing agent can reduce both the dye and the metal ions. However, the dye reduction is not a kinetically favored one and hence needs a catalyst. The metal clusters or the reduced metal ions serve the purpose. The dyes used as redox probes were methylene blue (MB), phenosafranin (PS), fluorescein (F), eosin (E) and rose Bengal (RB). If the dye solution is mixed with the reducing agents used, the color of the dye remains unaltered for 1–2 h indicating that the dye reduction, if occurs at all, is insignificant. Presence of surfactant also does not favor the dye reduction except for MB⁷⁴. However, dye reduction occurred very fast in presence of metal salts or metal sol. This signifies that under the experimental condition, the metal GME (which is produced *in situ* from the reduction of metal salt by the action of reducing agent) or FGME (already prepared particles and added from outside into the reaction mixture) plays the role of catalyst. This can be well monitored from the UV-visible spectra of the dye. Here, the usefulness of surfactant is also important. Firstly, this controls the growth of GME. Secondly, it repairs/prevents catalytic activity of GME/FGME from surface deactivation⁶⁸. And thirdly, specific dye-micelle interaction⁴⁵ leads to a selective catalytic reduction by GME/FGME catalyst. In the absence of the surfactant most of the reaction stopped or the progress decreased. When the dye and surfactants are oppositely charged, then the rate decreased with increasing surfactant concentration, but when they were of the same charge, then increase in the surfactant concentration generally increased the rate. When the rate of GME and FGME catalyzed rate involving a particular metal was considered, GME showed higher rate than FGME. The mechanism of this type of surfactant-mediated dye reduction with different reducing agents was nothing but the electron transfer from the reduction to the oxidant via metal nanoparticles. The details of the electron transfer process are described in the later phase of this article.

Growing metal particles as catalyst :

The reduction of different dyes was carried out in presence of AgNO₃ and the reducing agent, NaBH₄ in presence of surfactants, to study the catalytic activity of growing silver particles. The dye reduction was observed from the simultaneous decrease of the height of absorbance peak of the dye with increase of the silver plasmon peak at

390 nm (Fig. 7). It was also observed that for each case some induction time was observed to start the reduction and the rate of reduction in GME case was higher than FGME. The time required to start the reaction was not found in the absence of surfactants and the catalytic reduction started immediately after addition of NaBH_4 .

Fig. 7. Successive UV-visible spectra of the reduction of (a) methylene blue and (b) fluorescein; $[\text{MB}] = [\text{F}] = 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $[\text{AgNO}_3] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaBH}_4] = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

The rate of the catalysis by growing particles depends on a number of factors: not only the concentration of the reactants, catalyst precursor ion or the other reagents but also the nature of dye, surfactant, their electrical charges etc. For the reduction of PS, a cationic dye is faster with CTAB than with SDS. Similarly, reduction of DCF, an anionic dye, is faster with SDS than CTAB. The initial rates of reduction were determined for an anionic dye (F) with an anionic surfactant (SDS) and a cationic dye (MB) with a cationic surfactant. It is found that the rate of reduction increases with the increase in concentration of Ag^+ and BH_4^- and surfactant. The use of the surfactant delays the initiation of the catalytic process, although Ag^+ ions were present in the reaction medium from the very beginning. Again, stable particles (where no Ag^+ ion is supposed to be present in the presence of large excess of NaBH_4) can also catalyze the reduction. Furthermore, no catalyzed dye

reduction was observed in the presence of the reducing agents, viz. ascorbic acid and hydrazine. All these facts indicate that the growing particle, but not the Ag^+ ion, is the actual catalyst. During the course of growth when the size of silver particle reaches a certain critical level, the electrochemical standard potential of the (silver particle/silver ion) system becomes less negative compared to that of the weak reductant. Then, the latter gives up electrons reducing excess Ag^+ ion present in the system. The reducing agent (viz. BH_4^- ion) is also a strong one, and it can reduce simultaneously the Ag^+ ions and the dye. But the dye reduction is, however, kinetically not favored in the absence of silver particles. Therefore, here the growing silver particle plays the role of a true redox catalyst. One of the important observations of this study is the induction period, i.e. the time required to begin the catalytic dye reduction. The existence of such an induction period has been observed recently by Watzky and Finke⁸⁴ in the hydrogenation of cyclooctene in the presence of an Ir nanoparticle catalyst. Two possible factors might be responsible for the origin of the induction period, viz. a minimum concentration or a minimum or a minimum particle size requirement of the growing particle for catalysis. It should be mentioned that the induction period is observed only when surfactants are used as particle stabilizers, and it depends on both the nature of surfactant and dye. As a matter of fact, the minimum concentration or the minimum size is determined by the dye, taking into the account the influence of the surfactant on the formation of the particles. Unlike CTAB, SDS being an anionic surfactant, associates strongly compared to the silver ions. So a large number of embryo silver particles are formed leading to a higher number of particles. Zhai and Efrima⁸⁵ have reported similar type of effects of a number of surfactants and additives on the evolution and hence on the final size distribution of the particles. Therefore, for a given dye, the required minimum concentration is first met with SDS due to the formation of more particles in this systems. As a consequence, induction period is larger in SDS systems than in CTAB solutions. This lends support to the critical size requirement for the catalyst. This type of size effect is commonly observed for silver in photographic processes²². Besides, it has already been established that a small, critical particle size of the catalyst is required for faster ethylene hydrogenation⁸⁶.

For a given surfactant, the induction period again varies from dye to dye. It implies that it depends on the specific nature of the dye-particle interaction. Perhaps the surfactant plays a complex role in determining the nature of the dye-particle interaction which is not clear at present.

However, the presence of an induction period for stable particle catalyzed dye reductions seems to contradict the concept of minimum size requirement, since the size has al-

ready been attained in this case. But in no case, the induction period for stable particles was greater than that for growing particles. This indicates that some other factor might be contributing to the induction period. Probably, the encapsulation of stable particles by the surfactant poses some temporary barrier for the absorption of BH_4^- onto the particle. Aged stable particles on which this surfactant layer becomes thicker⁶⁸ show a larger induction period as compared to that of the freshly prepared stable silver particles. Thus, the induction period differs for the growing and stable particles. Increase in Ag particle and BH_4^- ion increases the number of reactants per organized assembly of surfactants, obviously leading to a faster growth process over the nucleation of the particles. On the other hand, increase in surfactant concentration has an opposite effect. Hence, the induction period decreases in the former two cases whereas it increases with increasing surfactant concentration.

To explain the rate of catalysis, we propose that electron transfer occurs via the growing particles, similar to (stable) colloid particle catalyzed redox reactions. The size-dependent redox potentials of the particles strongly depend on the medium too and govern the chemistry and catalytic activity of stabilized metal particles. Earlier work shows that the reduction potential of a silver wire decreases with the increase in BH_4^- concentration in water due to the absorption of BH_4^- ion onto the electrode surface⁸⁷. A similar effect is also expected in silver particles. However, the potential of growing particles containing BH_4^- adsorbed on their surface, unlike that for stable particles, will gradually increase with increasing nuclearity (size). The resultant potential of the particles with adsorbed BH_4^- will obviously be anodic to the reductant (BH_4^- ion) and cathodic to the oxidant (dye). Thus an electron relay via particle to dye is possible. Fig. 8 shows

Fig. 8. A model diagram for the electron transfer redox reaction via metal nanoparticles (GME).

the scheme of this electron transfer, where the growing particle in its intermediate stage accepts electrons from BH_4^- ions and conveys them to the dye.

The main focus of this report is the advantage of growing silver particles over stable silver particles as redox

catalysts. It is very difficult to compare the catalytic property of growing and stable particles because of the difficulty in determining the concentration and surface area of the catalysts. However, their catalytic property can be compared by taking the same initial concentration of precursor Ag^+ ions. In case of growing particles, some unreduced Ag^+ is always present. So the concentration of Ag^0 is always less in growing particles than the stable particles. In most cases, growing silver particles are found to be superior catalysts as compared to the stable particles. This behavior of growing particles may be attributed to the following two properties : firstly, its continuously renewable surface and, secondly, its large negative electrochemical potential which arises owing to the very small size. As usual, the rate of catalytic reduction should be determined by the difference in potential of the BH_4^- adsorbed particle and the potential of the oxidant system. The smaller the size of the particle the more is the potential difference, leading to a higher rate of reduction. Hence, the better catalytic activity of the growing particle is understood. Other reducing agents reduce Ag^+ ions. In fact, the efficiency of the BH_4^- ion is associated with its high electron injection capacity. Thus, it emphasizes the importance of the size-dependent redox potential of the catalyst particle. Lesser nucleophilic reducing agents could, in principle, reduce the dye only by their adsorption onto the particle at its early stages of formation. At a later stage, the electron injection capacity of these lesser nucleophilic reagents is insufficient to make the particle potential less negative than the potential of the dye to be reduced.

Other factors also play a role in determining the rate, viz. dye-surfactant and dye-particle interactions, difference in the catalyst concentration and the fraction of surface atoms etc. For example, the very slow rate of reduction when the dye and surfactant are of unlike charges, indicates the influence of the dye-surfactant interactions. Again, stable particles are superior catalysts when compared to growing particles for MB reduction. Whereas for PS it is true in CTAB only, in SDS growing particles are again superior catalysts over stable particles. Perhaps the strong interaction and adsorption of these two dyes (due to the presence of sulfur and nitrogen in the molecular skeleton) at the silver surface poison the growth of the particles in the embryo stage before attaining the required minimum size for the catalysis. As the stable particles are already formed, the question of such poisoning does not arise for them, which imparts the stable particles a better performance here. This also explains why the growing particle catalyzed dye reduction stops after some time in most cases, particularly in the absence of any surfactant. In the presence of surfactant, the dye can be adsorbed on the micellar surface, and thus this restricts its adsorption on the particle surface in the embryo stage. Moreover, proximity, favorable orien-

tation of the reactants relative to the hydrophobic surface of the particle, microscopic environment surrounding reacting molecules, the sensitivity of the surface structure etc., might have a direct bearing on the chemical reactivity.

Effect of growing and full grown metal particles on the redox probe :

The rate of the growing particle catalyzed reduction of anionic dyes was faster than that of stable particle catalyzed one in both aqueous and surfactant media. In fact, growing particles were found to be superior catalyst in most cases⁵³. Exceptions were noted in case of cationic dyes (PS and MB). For MB, stable, particle catalyzed reduction was faster in aqueous as well as surfactant media irrespective of the nature of the surfactant. To study the details of the catalytic activity of GME and FGME particles, we took another set of experiment using Pd particles. The redox catalytic properties of GME and FGME of Pd have been investigated in aqueous medium using the dye, MB and F as the redox probes. The catalytic rates for still growing and final particles are almost comparable for the MB-N₂H₄ system, but for F-NaBH₄ system, the catalytic rate is ~10 times faster by still growing particle than the final one, when all other conditions remain the same.

Dyes have strong influence on the still growing particle catalyzed reduction than the final particles. In the case of still growing particle catalyzed reduction, both the dye acts as strong catalyst/inhibitor/poison and the rate decreases with the increase in dye concentration. However, for final particle catalyzed reduction only MB acts as inhibitor.

The surface-to-volume ratio of small palladium particle is large compared to bulk metal. Hence, the adsorption of large number of foreign ions onto the nanoparticles surface is possible. This fact may lead to the large shift of redox potential when strong electronic interaction takes place between the adsorbed ion and the nanoparticles⁸³. Here, BH₄⁻ being a strong nucleophile and with high electron injection capacity (reduction potential is -1.33 V vs NHE) is chemisorbed on the Pd-nanoparticles surface and creates a dipolar layer. As a consequence, the Fermi potential of Pd nanoparticle increases, i.e. the reduction potential of Pd_{nanoparticle} / Pd^{II} system shifted to a more negative value. In this respect, influence of N₂H₄ is comparatively small as it is a weaker reducing agent (reduction potential is -0.7 V vs NHE). Similarly, adsorption of an oxidizing agent, i.e. dyes ($E_{1/2} \sim -0.3$ V vs NHE) onto the particle surface leads to an increase in the reduction potential as they are electrophilic in nature. In the reaction mixture, both the dye and the reducing agent are adsorbed at the particle surface and a resultant potential is adopted by the particles. However, for still growing particles, the resultant particle potential increases with the increasing agglomeration number of the particle as the inherent particle potential itself increases

with the increasing particle size. This resultant potential becomes intermediate to the dye and the reducing agent and so the particle potential becomes anodic to the reducing agent and cathodic to the dye. Thus the electron transfer between the reducing agent and the dye becomes possible via palladium particles.

As the rates do not change with stirring, it shows that catalytic reductions are surface-controlled. The rate of reduction of this type of surface-controlled reactions depends on the difference in resultant potential of the Pd nanoparticle and the potential of the dye, according to the following equation⁸⁸,

$$\text{Rate} \propto e^{(1-\alpha)\eta F/RT} \quad (1)$$

where, α is the transfer coefficient, η the overpotential and F , R , T have their usual meanings. Here η depends on the difference of the reduction potential of Pd-particle (here it is the mixed potential) and dye. For final Pd-particle catalyzed reductions, the mixed reduction potential of Pd-particle depends on $E_{1/2}$ value of the reducing agent/dye which becomes adsorbed onto the particle surface. The final Pd-particle catalyzed rates of MB-N₂H₄ and F-NaBH₄ system cannot be compared as the ΔE values are different for the two cases.

Dependence of rates with reactant concentrations is established earlier for this type of surface controlled reactions^{25,26}. The order dependence is fractional. In our case no such law was obeyed. The obvious reason is the distribution of reactants (dye and reducing agent) between the catalyst surface and bulk water. In aqueous micelle, similar type of distribution occurs for organic compounds/micellar counter ions/H⁺/OH⁻ between the micellar surface and bulk water^{89,44,45}. The distribution of compounds or ions is directly related to the ion exchange constant. Here same type of ion exchange equilibrium is expected to occur which can be expressed as

$$K = \text{Dye}_w.R_s/\text{Dye}_s.R_w \quad (2)$$

where R is the reducing agent, and subscripts w and s indicate concentrations in bulk water and catalyst surface, respectively. So, the concentration of dye/reducing agent on the catalyst surface is a complex function of their bulk concentration. However, some of the observed results can be explained qualitatively by this model. Dyes are more hydrophobic compared to the reducing agents and so their adsorption is more favorable on the hydrophobic wall of the Pd-particles. This shows the poisoning of the catalyst whereas the reducing agent is not at all affected. Between MB and F, MB has higher poisoning effect due to the presence of S in its skeleton and more favorable Pd-S interaction can be presumed. For a particular dye concentration, increase in catalyst concentration increases the catalyst surface area, generating more vacant sites onto the catalyst surface. As a consequence, concentrations of dye and

reducing agent at the catalyst surface are altered. For a low catalyst concentration, catalyst surface will be covered only by hydrophobic dye due to its hydrophobicity and as the catalyst concentration increases both the dye and reducing agent are adsorbed at the catalyst surface. So, the rate increases with the $[Pd^{II}]$. Similarly, change in surface concentrations of dye and reducing agent occurs when [reducing agent] or [dye] increases for a particular catalyst concentration. However, the MB adsorption on the still growing Pd is so strong that it is not easily replaced by even higher $[N_2H_4]$. As a consequence, rate is almost independent of $[N_2H_4]$.

The above results can explain the difference in catalytic properties of the catalytic performance for still growing and final particle. For comparison we used the same concentration of Pd^{II} . At first it is to be remembered that the active catalyst concentration is not same in both the cases. In the still growing case, all the precursor Pd^{II} ions are not converted into metal particles and so the concentration of Pd^0 is less in still growing case. Even the higher rates are observed for still growing case (for F- $NaBH_4$ system). This indicates the influence of particle size on catalysis. The smaller size particles have more negative reduction potential compared to the final particle and hence the overpotential (η) value (eq. 1) will be higher. As a result, rate will be higher particles.

Another important factor is the influence of dye on the growth of the catalyst particles through their adsorption. This is why the reduction rate decreases with the increase in dye concentration. At the initial stage of particle growth, the $[Pd\text{-particle}]/[dye]$ ratio will be low and so dye provides more effective poisoning action to the catalyst particle. As a result, poisoning action of dye is more prominent in still growing particle. This fact is more prominent in MB rather than F. This is because MB is adsorbed more easily onto the Pd surface due to the presence of sulfur in its skelton. The autocatalytic rate for still growing Pd-particle catalyzed MB reduction can also be explained by this type of dye adsorption. As time passes, the $[Pd\text{-particle}]/[dye]$ ratio gradually increases and so the rate also increases autocatalytically. Now it can be said that dyes, which have stonger affinity to the growing metal particle surface, will poison the particle surface more effectively, through adsorption.

To examine the useful application of metal nanoparticles, reductions of nitro compounds like 2-nitrophenol, 4-nitrophenol, 4-nitroaniline, 4-nitrotolune, 2,4-dinitrophenol were done successfully in presence of both growing (GME) and full-grown (FGME) coinage metal nanoparticles using $NaBH_4$ as reducing agent. For all the cases, their amino derivatives were the sole product⁴². The above nitro compounds are inert to $NaBH_4$ alone. But in presence of the metal particles like Cu, Ag or Au, the yellow colour of the

nitro compounds vanished which speaks for the reduction of nitro compounds. To study the kinetics for both the GME and FGME catalyzed reactions we used 4-nitrophenol (4NP) as a representative substrate. In $NaBH_4$ medium (pH >10.0), the peak of 4NP (λ_{max} 317 nm) is red-shifted due to the formation of 4-nitrophenolate ion (λ_{max} 400 nm). As the reaction was over involving GME, the peak at 400 nm vanished and a new peak in the blue region appeared due to the corresponding amino compound (λ_{max} 290 nm). This was confirmed by superimposing the spectrum of the pure amino compound under indentical condition. Interestingly, the plasmon band (~ 380 nm) due to silver hydrosol appeared only after the complete reduction of the substrate. The plasmon band of silver remained masked by the absorption band of nitro compounds in solution. However, in case of gold, the plasmon band appeared (~ 510 nm) before the reduction and became visible even in the presence of nitro compounds. The kinetics of the reduction involving ultra-trace concentrations of the adhered particles were comparable to FGMEs. To observe the plasmon bands, the concentration of metal in the reaction mixture was maintained in the $\sim 10^{-6}$ M range. However, TEM images of the metal particles could not be photographed because of their low concentration in the reaction mixture.

Fig. 9. A kinetic change representation of GME (Au and Ag) catalyzed reduction of 4-nitrophenol.

For all the metal cases, the reaction followed a zero order kinetics having some induction time with respect to the substrate when growing metal particles were used as the catalyst. But when FGME was used in N_2 atmosphere, the reaction proceeds with a first order kinetics without any induction time. But in oxygen atmosphere FGME showed again a zero order kinetics with some induction period. Interestingly, if to the reaction mixture of FGME and $NaBH_4$, the substrate is added at different intervals of time, the reaction kinetics change from zero to first order. When the reaction follows a zero order kinetics there remains an induction time. When the progress of the reaction (Fig. 9) is

closely monitored, it is observed that the reaction starts with some induction time and then the rate of the reaction increases to some extent. After that, the rate becomes independent with the course of the reaction. This is observed in all the metal cases.

In case of the GME catalyzed reaction, catalyst particles were first formed and they started to agglomerate. So it always needed some time to reach the optimum size to catalyze the reaction. This time became more prominent when surfactants like TX-100 or CTAB were used. For the case of FGME, no IT was observed when the reaction was performed in nitrogen atmosphere. However, in air, the metal nanoparticles gets oxidized in presence of nucleophile like BH_4^- . The surface coated oxide layer of the metal particles hindered the catalysis. So, the same reducing agent BH_4^- again reduced the oxide layer and regenerated the catalyst particles with fresh surface. This regeneration of catalyst surface was responsible for the induction time in FGME catalyzed reactions. The reduction immediately started as soon as the metal particles of appropriate size were formed. More the catalyst particles formed more was the reaction rates and hence the rate of the reaction increased after the end of the IT. As soon as the particle started transferring electron from reductant to oxidant, that particle could not take part in the coalescence process. The coalescence process for the growth of metal particles became slower compared to the reduction of nitro compounds into their amino derivative. So the reaction kinetics changed to zero order with respect to the nitro compound. However, the reaction kinetics were changed from zero order to first order for the case of FGME with excess of NaBH_4 or some time should be given for NaBH_4 to reduce the oxide layer of the particle surface. This formed a fresh surface with strong adsorption of BH_4^- onto the particle surface. As the reductant was strongly adsorbed, the rate of the reaction only depended on the oxidant and hence the reaction kinetics followed first order with respect to the substrate. This kinetic pattern remained same for all the coinage metal nanoparticles. However, it became faster in case of Au and slower for Cu.

It is known that micelle increases the suspendability of metal nanoparticles (stabilization) and thus helps to study to reaction kinetics⁴². Micelle sometimes refreshes the surface of catalyst particles⁶⁸. So we studied the reaction in three different micelles. When the aqueous system was replaced by an anionic micelle, such as SDS, adsorption of the phenolate ion onto the nanoparticle surface was not disturbed. This happened due to the negatively charged micellar surface, which prevented the incorporation of the substrate in SDS micelle. So the reduction rate in SDS was comparable to that in aqueous medium. In cationic micelle (CTAB), however, due to the presence of both hydro-

phobic and hydrophilic attraction between the phenolate ion and the positively charged micellar surface, adsorption of the substrate onto the catalyst particles became restricted, so the rate decreased to a considerable extent. On the other hand, in a nonionic micelle, an intermediate rate was observed, because only hydrophobic interaction was operative in nonionic micelle between the substrate and the uncharged micellar surface. Thus the reaction rates in three different micelles followed the order : $\text{SDS} > \text{TX-100} > \text{CTAB}$. However, the location of the substrate, phenolate ion in micelle could be quantified from the shift of acid-base equilibrium⁴⁵.

Summary and conclusion

A precise explanation of this catalytic effect is a difficult undertaking. It necessitates more experimental as well as theoretical studies. Nevertheless, this study has revealed that (i) at a certain point of their growth, the particles become catalytic, (ii) the growing particles are more catalytic than stable particles, and (iii) strong catalyst surface-substrate interaction is essential for an effective catalytic process. However, the nature of surfactant and the reducing agents too influence the catalytic property of growing particles. Judicious selection of a surfactant may result in its enhanced or suppressed catalytic efficiency for a given reactant (dye). This report also indicates that the choice of proper nucleophilic reducing agent for a particular metal could give unique catalytic selectivity. Thus, growing metal particles emerge as a new generation catalyst with their distinct advantages over stable final particles. In conventional electrochemistry, a constancy in the reduction potential value due to $\text{M}^{\text{III}}/\text{M}$ (vs NHE) is always taken for granted at a particular temperature. But segregation of bulk metal in their narrow size domain gives rise to size-dependent redox potential values (potential becomes variable) leading to interesting properties. The studies on the chemisorption of different molecules on the small metal particles substantiate the specific interaction in aqueous solution. This specific interaction leads to a change in the chemical reactivity of metal particles. Thus a metal particle with the variable size domain may serve as catalyst for so many reactions because of the size-dependent redox potential value. Depending upon the size, a small metal particle can store different number of excess electrons and positive holes and also change their redox potential upon surface modification, often photo-emit electrons and sensitize the photochemical transformation of other solutes.

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References

1. E. H. Cordes and R. B. Dunlap, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1969, **2**, 329.
2. E. J. Fendler and J. H. Fendler, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 271.
3. W. P. Jencks, "Catalysis in Chemistry and Enzymology", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1969.
4. D. G. Hall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 4287, and references 1-4 therein.
5. J. H. Fendler and E. J. Fendler, "Catalysis in Micellar and Macromolecular Systems", Academic, New York, 1975.
6. G. S. Hartley, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, **30**, 444.
7. R. B. Dunlap and E. H. Cordes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 4395.
8. C. A. Bunton, L. Robinson, J. Schaak and M. F. Stam, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1971, **36**, 2346.
9. M. T. A. Behme and E. H. Cordes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 260.
10. L. R. Romsted and E. H. Cordes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 4404.
11. A. P. Alivisatos, *Science*, 1996, **271**, 933.
12. A. P. Alivisatos, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 13226.
13. S. H. Kim, G. Medeiros-Ribeiro, D. A. Ohlberg, R. A. Williams and Z. R. Heath, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1999, **103**, 10341.
14. W. P. McConnel, J. P. Novak, L. C. Brousseau III, R. R. Fuieler, R. C. Tenent and D. L. Feldheim, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2000, **104**, 8925.
15. A. Henglein, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1997, **101**, 1562.
16. "Clusters and Colloids", ed. G. Schmid, VCH, Weinheim, 1994.
17. P. Mulvaney, *Langmuir*, 1996, **12**, 788.
18. S. C. Davis, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 153.
19. M. D. Morse, *Chem. Rev.*, 1986, **86**, 1049.
20. A. Henglein, *Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **89**, 1861.
21. G. Schmid, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 1709.
22. M. Mostafavi, J. L. Marignier, J. Amblard and J. Belloni, *Radiat. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **34**, 605.
23. J. Belloni, *Curr. Opin. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1996, **1**, 184.
24. A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 1709.
25. M. Spiro, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1979, 1507.
26. M. Spiro and P. L. Freund, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1983, 1649.
27. P. L. Freund and M. Spiro, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 1074.
28. P. L. Freund and M. Spiro, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1986, 2277.
29. D. S. Miller, A. J. Bard, G. McLendon and J. Ferguson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 5336.
30. L. N. Lewis, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 2693.
31. A. Henglein and R. Tausch-Treml, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1981, **80**, 84.
32. F. Zaera, A. J. Gellman and G. A. Somorjai, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1986, **19**, 24.
33. S. J. Tauster, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **26**, 389.
34. G. C. Bond, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **26**, 490.
35. T. Sun and K. Seff, *Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **94**, 2833.
36. D. M. Hercules, A. Proctor and M. Houalla, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1994, **27**, 387.
37. H. Hirai, Y. Nakao and N. Toschima, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem.*, (A) 1979, **13**, 633.
38. M. Komiyama and H. Hirai, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1983, **56**, 2833.
39. P. Ball, *Nature*, 1991, **349**, 101.
40. T. Pal, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1994, **71**, 679.
41. J. H. Fendler, *Chem. Rev.*, 1987, **87**, 877.
42. N. Pradhan, A. Pal and T. Pal, *Langmuir*, 2001, **17**, 1800.
43. K. Mallick, Z. L. Wong and T. Pal, *J. Photochem. Photobio. A*, 2001, **140**, 75.
44. T. Pal, S. De, N. R. Jana, N. Pradhan, R. Mandal, A. Pal, A. E. Beezer and J. C. Mitchell, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 4724.
45. T. Pal and N. R. Jana, *Langmuir*, 1996, **12**, 3114.
46. D. S. Millar and G. J. McLendon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 6791.
47. P. Mulvaney, T. Linnert and A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 7843.
48. J. Huang and J. C. Hemminger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 3342.
49. J. Huang, D. A. Dahlgren and J. C. Hemminger, *Langmuir*, 1994, **10**, 626.
50. G. Harrison, B. J. Haylett and J. King, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1983, **75**, 265.
51. A. Coupy, B. Tchoubar and A. Astrae, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 1141.
52. P. A. Greico, P. Garner and Z. M. He, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 1897.
53. N. R. Jana and T. Pal, *Curr. Sci.*, 1998, **75**, 145.
54. N. R. Jana, L. Gearheart and C. J. Murphy, 2001, **7**, 617.
55. D. G. Duff and A. Baiker, *Langmuir*, 1993, **9**, 2301.
56. P. Mulvaney and A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 4182.
57. P. Mulvaney and A. Henglein, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1990, **168**, 391.
58. J. Belloni, *Radiat. Res.*, 1998, **150**, S9.
59. G. V. Buston and R. M. Sellers, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **22**, 195.
60. G. Elisabeth, H. Remita, J. Khalouri, B. Keita, L. Nadjo and J. Belloni, *New J. Chem.*, 1998, 1257.
61. A. Pal, *Talanta*, 1998, **46**, 583.
62. K. Esumi, T. Tano, K. Torigoe and K. Meguro, *Chem. Mater.*, 1990, **2**, 564.
63. A. Henglein, *Israel J. Chem.*, 1993, **33**, 77.
64. U. Kreibig and M. Volmer, "Optical Properties of Metal Clusters", Springer, Berlin, 1995.
65. M. Faraday, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. London*, 1857, **147**, 145.
66. N. R. Jana, T. K. Sau and T. Pal, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1999, **103**, 115.
67. T. Linnert, P. Mulvaney and A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 679.
68. T. Pal, T. K. Sau and N. R. Jana, *Langmuir*, 1997, **13**, 1481.
69. H. Hirai, Y. Nakao, N. Toshima and K. Adachi, *Chem. Lett.*, 1967, 905.
70. P. V. Kamat, M. Flumiani and G. V. Hartland, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1998, **102**, 3123.
71. S. L. Logunov, T. S. Ahmadi, A. El-Sayed, J. T. Khoury and R. L.

- Whetten, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1997, **101**, 3713.
72. S. Link and M. A. El-Sayed, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1999, **103**, 4212.
73. L. Francois, M. Mostafavi and J. Belloni, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2000, **104**, 6133.
74. N. R. Jana, Z. L. Wang and T. Pal, *Langmuir*, 2000, **16**, 2457.
75. K. R. Brown and M. J. Natan, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 726.
76. R. G. Freeman, M. B. Hommer, K. C. Grabar, M. A. Jackson and M. J. Natan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 718.
77. A. Henglein and D. Meisel, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 7392.
78. K. R. Brown, D. G. Walter and M. J. Natan, *Chem. Mater.*, 2000, **12**, 306.
79. K. R. Brown and M. J. Natan, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 726.
80. D. V. Goia and E. Matijevic, *Colloids Surfaces A-Physicochem. Eng. Aspects*, 1999, **146** 139.
81. Y. Zhou, C. Y. Wang, Y. R. Zhu and Z. Y. Chen, *Chem. Mater.*, 1999, **11**, 2310.
82. N. R. Jana, A. Pal, Z. L. Wang and T. Pal, *J. Nanoparticle Res.*, 2000, 0000
83. N. R. Jana and T. Pal, *Langmuir*, 1999, **15**, 3458.
84. M. A. Watzky and E. G. Finke, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 10382.
85. X. Zhaz and S. Efrima, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 10235, 10382.
86. M. Che and C. O. Bennett, *Adv. Catal.*, 1989, **36**, 55.
87. C. G. Blatchford, O. Siimon and M. Kerker, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **97**, 2503.
88. P. W. Atkins, "Physical Chemistry", ELBS, Oxford, 1990.
89. L. S. Romsred, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 5170.